

Sustained Self-sensing and Autonomous Self-healing via Electro-thermal Coupling in Fiber-composites

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24th International Conference on Composite Materials
August 4th, 2025

Outline

- Motivation / Background
- Thermal Coupling of Sensing and Healing Agents
- 3D-printing and Composite Fabrication
- Repeatable and *in situ* Self-sensing + Self-healing
 - Effect of Healing Temperature
 - Self-sensing Damage to Automate Self-repair
- Summary / Conclusions

Motivation

Aerospace

Automotive

Naval

Civil

Energy

Motivation/Background

Layered architecture

Compos. Struct. **79** (2007)

Difficult to detect & repair

www.dsto.defence.gov.au

Self-healing Materials

Extrinsic

Intrinsic

Annu. Rev. Mater. Res. **40** (2010)

Soft Materials

Structural Materials

Angew. Chem. **51** (2012)

Science **295** (2002)

Interfacial contact enables room-temp repair

Requires external energy (e.g., heat)

Fracture damage

ASM International (2010) *Polymer* **53** (2012)

Catastrophic failure

USAF Hilltop Times

Self-sensing Materials

Manual Detection Strategies

Compos. Sci. Technol. **139** (2017)

Adv. Mater. **28** (2016)

Remote Detection Strategies

Chem. Mater. **35** (2023)

Compos. B Eng. **177** (2019)

Concurrent Self-healing + Self-sensing

- Repeatable **self-sensing** and **self-healing** has been largely limited to **soft (non-structural)** materials.

Soft Materials (Damage sensing & *in situ* Self-healing)

Key Challenges

1. **Self-sensing** and **self-healing** in **structural materials** has not achieved the following features simultaneously:

- (I) *In situ*
- (II) Repeatable
- (III) Autonomous

2. Self-sensing techniques largely **detect damage**, but **do not detect healing** (i.e., structural repair).

3. Current sensing techniques cannot **differentiate crack closure** from **structural repair**.

Pristine

Cut

Healed

Structural Materials (Damage sensing & *ex situ* Self-healing)

Single Cycle *Ex Situ* Healing Interleaves

Compos. Part A 185 (2024)

Compos. Part A 165 (2023)

Ex Situ = outside the service environment requiring human intervention (in oven/hot press).

Repeatable *in situ* Thermal Remending Technique

- Intrinsic healing of poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) enables **unprecedented repeatability** for *in situ* self-healing.

3D-printing onto preform substrate

Pristine multifunctional composite laminate

100 *in situ* Heal Cycles (Order of magnitude)

Internal delamination damage

Self-healing via *in situ* thermal remending

- (I) *In situ*
- (II) Repeatable
- (III) Autonomous

[1] *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **151** (2017)

[2] *Mater. Today Comm.* **8** (2020)

[3] *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **295** (2010)

New Approach: Electrical Sensing + Thermal Healing

- Concurrent **sensing + healing** can be achieved through combined action of a **conductive polymer (cP)** fiber sensor and **EMAA** healing agent

Fine Tuning of Thermal Properties

- **Coupling thermal properties** of sensing and healing agents is required **below** the T_g of the host FRP.

- **EMAA is orders of magnitude less viscous** than **cP** at the target healing temperature.

- **Bi-modal peaks** in electrical resistance occur at the **onset of melting** and the **completion of recrystallization**.

3D-printing and Composite Fabrication

- Fused deposition modeling (FDM) is utilized to precisely **print** EMAA patterns directly onto reinforcement and cP sensing stitches.

Printing directly on woven fabric

Continuous Serpentine Pattern

24% areal coverage

Completed prints with high precision

cP Sensing Stitches

“Hairpin” Design

Woven Reinforcement

Layup and Composite Fabrication

Self-healing GFRP layup

$[0/90]_2/H/0/90/0/EMAA/90/0/90/H/[0/90]_2$

cP Sensing Stitches

Vacuum Infusion

Curing conditions: 24h @ RT + 2h @ 121°C + 3h @ 177°C $T_g = 141^\circ\text{C}$

Sensor Behavior

- 2x2 sensor geometries achieve a **reliable sensing** resistance signal at a 130°C-healing temperature.

Mechanical

Electrical

Thermal

- Large resistance peak only occurs when reaching the target 130°C healing temperature (T_h) enabling healing to be “sensed” (vs. crack closure).

Autonomous Sensing + Healing Protocol

- The **electrical resistance** sensing signal is utilized to **automate** the **detection / repair** process.

Mechanical

Thermal

Load/Unload

Heat

Cool

Automated Self-sensing + Self-healing

- Achieved **100 automated** and *in situ* self-sensing / self-healing cycles.

- Sensor performance improves while healing efficiency sustains at **80%** of toughened virgin G_{IC} .

Summary / Conclusions

- Designed a structural composite with **concurrent** and **repeatable damage detection** and **self-repair**.
- **Coupled** thermal properties of **sensing** and **healing** agents with **composite host**.
- Tuned **healing temperature** to achieve a reliable **signal confirmation** of **successful healing**.
- Utilized sensor electrical resistance measurements to **automate** the self-healing process.
- Achieved **100 consecutive *in situ* self-sensing + self-healing cycles**—the first time in a **structural composite**.

Turicek et al. Sustained Self-sensing and Autonomous Self-healing via Electro-thermal Coupling in Fiber-composites. *In Prep.* (2025).

Acknowledgements

Funding Source:

U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
Strategic Environmental Research and Defense Program (SERDP)
Weapons Systems and Platforms (WP)
Grant # W912HQ21C0044

**US Army Corps
of Engineers®**

Multifunctional Composites Group
Innovating Materials & Structures

Academic Collaborators:

Prof. Patrick

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Prof. Therriault

Negar

International Conference of Self-healing Materials (ICSHM2026)

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials
July 8-10
Drexel University, Philadelphia, USA

Event highlights:

- Connect with experts and peers from around the world
- Discover emerging technologies, methods, and applications
- Present your latest research and gain valuable feedback
- Explore historic city - Philadelphia, PA birthplace of the United States

 July 8-10, 2026

 Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, USA

 <https://icshm2026.org>

Abstract Submission Open: Now
Abstract Submission Close: 15 February 2026

JULY 8-10

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials

Conference Chairs

Prof. Jason Patrick
(NC State University)

Prof. Amir Farnham
(Drexel University)

Questions

Back Up Slides

Sensor Geometry

- 1x1, 1x2, 2x2 sensor geometries are investigated to achieve a **reliable sensing** resistance signal at a 130°C-healing temperature.

Limited spreading and physical interconnect of sensor enables repeated restoration with **unprecedented repeatability**.

Pressure delivery mechanism in EMAA enables spreading of the healing agent for **improved healing** with continued cycling.

- 2x2 sensor geometry** achieved the best performance with **repeatable** electrical restoration **below 10kΩ** enabling **off-the-shelf** measuring equipment.

Experimental Controls

No EMAA

No cPLA

Yes Heat

No EMAA

Yes cPLA

Yes Heat

Yes EMAA

No cPLA

Yes Heat

Yes EMAA

Yes cPLA

No Heat

Experimental Controls

Sample 1

Sample 2

Sample 3

Sample 4

Sample 5

Fiber Debris Accumulation

- Fiber debris accumulation in crack plane inhibits EMAA remending leading to a progressive decline in healing performance

Virgin Fracture and *In Situ* Self-Healing Behavior

- Virgin fracture resistance & healing efficiency scale w/ EMAA areal coverage

3D Printed Pattern

Fracture direction

8H Satin Weave

Interlaminar Toughening Performance

- Areal coverage and thickness dominates global toughening while orientation controls local crack propagation behavior

- Up to **450%** increase in interlaminar fracture resistance!

- L vs. T less pronounced at higher areal coverages

Topological Investigation of Healing Performance

- Fiber-reinforcement type influences self-healing behavior

Virgin Cycle (V)

*scale bars = 50 μm

Heal Cycle 5 (H5)

Heal Cycle 10 (H10)

Heal Cycle 20 (H20)

Comparison of GFRP and CFRP Healing Performance

- 100 heal cycles achieved in GFRP (and CFRP) w/o significant degradation in recovery

Numerical vs. Experimental Thermal Comparison

- **Thermal simulations** performed in COMSOL show good agreement **within 5°C** of the **midline surface temperature** when compared to experiments.

Resistive Heating Investigation

- Since infrared (IR) camera measures surface temperature, 3D nonlinear Finite Element (FE) simulations[†] conducted to resolve through-thickness thermal profile in glass- (GFRP) and carbon-fiber (CFRP) composites

[†] w/ Prof. K. Nakshatrala (Univ. Houston)

Structural Integrity: In-Plane Tension

- Investigate effect of composite modification(s) on in-plane tensile performance†

Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

$n = 3$

28

† ASTM D-3039

In-plane Tensile Performance

- EMAAs inclusions have **minimal impact** on **in-plane tensile** performance

Note

- EMAAs at maximum **36% areal coverage** (~ 2 vol%) for this study

- Bilinear stress vs. strain response is nearly **indistinguishable** between EMAAs toughened and plain composites
- Initial modulus, final modulus, and ultimate tensile strength exhibit **<5% difference**